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The Analysis of Understanding English Reading Text In Uinsu Students MPI Prodi 2

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to understand how to increase the understanding of how to read English for students of the second semester of the Islamic Education Management study program, so that they can read comfortably, understand the meaning of each word, sentence and paragraph without looking at the dictionary when reading. carried out using qualitative methods starting from direct observation to the MPI 2 student class, interviews were also carried out with several students, and finally we took documentation during the interview process, so that we received the correct results. The achievements of this research show that students' English reading comprehension has improved significantly from the previous semester, students have also understood the meaning of English reading texts by just listening to them. The method they use to improve their understanding is by continuing to read English regularly, and memorizing lists of words. By increasing the list of words, we as students can improve our reading comprehension. These are the two methods that the average student uses.

Keywords : *English Reading, Comprehension, Students*

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INTRODUCTION

Language is an important means of communication. English is an international language and this language is a means of oral and written communication. English language proficiency is the ability to understand spoken and written language and is expressed in four forms: listening, speaking, reading, and writing (Dalimunthe & Ihsan, 2021). Learning English does not only involve planning, implementation, and evaluation, but also support capacity. professional staff and infrastructure (Sya & Helmanto, 2020). Foreign language teaching has developed in Indonesia in line with society's need for the importance of language skills in the era of globalization (Adnyana, 2022). In the context of teaching English as a foreign language, one of the teaching focuses is speaking skill besides the three other skills, namely listening, reading and writing (Rahmawati, 2020).

Writing seems to be a rather difficult language skill, requiring a high level of ability to express thoughts, ideas and emotions and create sentences. Knowledge of English is necessary not only in school classes but also in everyday life. Language plays an important role in life and existence because humans use language to convey messages and obtain information through communication (Suprihatin, 2022). Writing is an activity of expressing thoughts, ideas and feelings with written words. The components of a language include vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation. Therefore, these language skills and components can be applied in daily activities (Shafira & Santoso, 2021). Writing skills in English are the most difficult skills because they require other skills that are productive in learning English. Writing activities are different from listening, speaking and reading activities. Because, in writing there are many linguistic aspects that must be considered in order to convey ideas that can be understood and self-realized to the reader (Yulia, 2017).

In addition, results written in English can be used as a medium to disseminate news and scientific information to the public in accordance with current developments. One of the aspects of language involved in writing is grammar and vocabulary. This means that writing provides an excellent opportunity for students to further develop their understanding of grammar (Obisuru &

Purbani, 2016). Optimizing these skills will make it easier to practice these skills, for example by Pay attention to sentence structure when practicing reading comprehension. Therefore, when reading a book, you not only need to know the content of the story and the vocabulary you are reading, but also practice your knowledge of sentence structure. Writing in English becomes easier if you understand the correct sentence structure(Sya, Anoeграjekti, et al., 2022).

Speaking is the ability to express and convey thoughts, ideas and emotions by pronouncing articulatory sounds and words. In simple terms, speaking can be defined as the ability to convey messages to other people through spoken words. Speaking is also a process of thinking and reasoning that allows a person's speech to be well received and understood by other people and listeners (Hartiwi et al., 2015). Speaking ability is a factor that greatly influences the quality of the ability to convey information orally. Speakers must have the ability and skills to convey information to other people. This means that the speaker needs to really understand how to speak coherently and effectively so that listeners can effectively understand the information conveyed by the speaker.

As an aspect of language, speaking plays an important role in social life, so that everyone must easily acquire the ability to speak. (B, 2014) Speaking ability is a factor that greatly influences the quality of the ability to convey information orally. Speakers must have the ability and skills to convey information to other people. This means that the speaker needs to really understand how to speak coherently and effectively so that listeners can effectively understand the information conveyed by the speaker. As an aspect of language, speaking plays an important role in social life, so that everyone must easily acquire the ability to speak (Wahya, 1970). The variety of speaking strategies that can be used is interactive and collaborative language learning interactions are the best way to improve speaking skills (Mufidah, 2017). People who are fluent in English are willing to easily communicate with foreigners, are able to understand the culture of other countries, and actively use English in daily interactions in the classroom while learning English (Amrullah, 2015).

METHOD

This research took place at UINSU campus II, MPI 2 semester 2 study program, precisely on Jl William Iskandar, Pasar VI Percut Sei Tuan District, Medan City, North Sumatra Province. This research took place quickly within one day on May 15 2024. Researchers used qualitative method, where research directly observes the research location, namely the MPI 2 semester 2 class, after that interviews with resource persons, namely students, the interview process goes well and quickly, then documentation as proof of the process of observations and interviews that have taken place, documentation is taken when interview process with sources and after the interview process is complete.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Students' knowledge regarding English-based academic reading comprehension is at a basic level. Causes of lack of comprehension include a small word list and frequent reading of Indonesian texts. Specifically, students in the MPI 2 Semester 2 class were asked questions about difficulties in reading English reading comprehension texts. These texts usually support students' academic reading activities. If you look, the difficulties of MPI 2 Semester 2 students start from difficulties before, during and after reading. Difficulties at the beginning, MPI 2 Semester 2 students had difficulty choosing reading material and the reading material was too thick so students were lazy to read. The biggest difficulty is that while reading, most students do not understand the vocabulary in the reading. The sentences are too long and difficult to understand. One student also thought the reading was too abstract. This is because academic reading is different from other types of reading and the length and level of text varies at different stages. These texts are abstract and challenging because they have a philosophy expressed in complex language, which causes students to get bored, and not be interested in reading anymore. After reading, students also have difficulty picking up important points in the reading and how to summarize the reading in their own language. So reading comprehension in the MPI 2 Semester 2 class decreases, but MPI 2 Semester 2 students will be more active and try to improve their reading comprehension and reduce their feeling of laziness.

Based on the results of research activities, it was found that the cause of students' reading comprehension difficulties in MPI 2 class, these factors can be seen from internal factors (within the student) and external factors (outside the student). The internal factors are interest and activity in reading activities, and differences in abilities of students. On campus, specifically in the MPI 2 class,

there are still many children who have difficulty understanding English reading comprehension, due to their lack of interest in reading books. Cultivating an interest in reading in the classroom is not an easy thing, but it still has to be worked on and this requires cooperation between teachers and students.

Meanwhile, external factors are the facilities and infrastructure owned by students in the MPI 2 class and the campus and family environment. In essence, each person's understanding ability is different. A person's comprehension ability depends on their vocabulary, eye range, previous background, interest, speed, purpose of reading, flexibility in regulating speed, familiarity with the ideas being read and intellectual ability. These factors can come from internal and external. Other internal factors include interest, intelligence, attitude, talent, motivation, and so on. And external factors include social and economic background, reading facilities and infrastructure, and reading habits. Several factors influence reading ability, namely physiological factors, intelligence factors, environmental factors and psychological factors. The solution obtained from the teaching staff who teach in MPI 2 classes to overcome MPI 2 students who lack English reading comprehension and who have difficulty in reading comprehension is to focus students on reading activities and make students interested in reading activities. And encouragement and motivation from teaching staff and parents of students is needed. Apart from that, evaluation at the end of the lesson is to find out what the students' abilities are. The role of parents in providing motivation and providing facilities for various types of reading books at home is very important. With motivation from parents, children will feel enthusiastic and try to learn. Parents' efforts to create a situation of interest in children's learning is by providing support to children so that they have high awareness that comes from themselves, parents who have a great interest in learning activities.

Apart from that, the solution or effort to overcome students' difficulties regarding their lack of English reading comprehension is that teaching staff can apply appropriate learning models, strategies and methods to develop students' reading skills in the MPI 2 Stambuk 2023 class. Various learning models can be applied by One of the teaching staff is the POE (Predict Observe Explain) learning model. which refers to constructivist learning theory. In this learning model, students build their own initial knowledge with the help of educators. Educators play a role in exploring students' reading comprehension by providing the main tasks, namely, predict, observe and explain. At the predicting stage, students will predict/guess what will happen to an example of a problem presented by the teaching staff and write it down on a sheet and then collect it with the teaching staff. In the next stage of observing, the lecturer will form a group. They will carry out an experiment or practice related to the problem examples given by the lecturer. Experiments are carried out to observe and test the correctness of predictions that students have previously written. The lecturer guides students according to the work steps that have been set, and in the final stage, namely the explaining stage. After carrying out the experiment in small groups that have been formed, each group will write down the results of the experiment and develop a hypothesis from the results of the experiment. Next, they explained the difference between initial predictions and the results of experiments carried out by the POE learning model which can improve students' reading skills. The Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) strategy is one component of Whole Language. Sustained

Silent Reading (SSR) was developed by Routman and Frooze which is an activity of reading silently. SSR is an activity that students do by reading silently. In this activity, students are given the opportunity to choose the book or material they will read themselves. Students choose English reading books that suit their abilities so that they can finish reading the reading. Therefore, lecturers provide interesting reading material from various books or sources wherever possible so that students can choose reading material. This will make students more interested in carrying out reading activities because students themselves will choose the books they will read.

Ghearnurma revealed that the SSR strategy can develop and improve the reading comprehension abilities of students in MPI 2 class. The SQ3R (Survey, Question, Reading, Recite, and Review) method was designed by Robinson in 1961. SQ3R is a method to improve students' understanding of reading content . In this method, what is done is skimming, asking, reading, answering, and reviewing again. The SQ3R method is more effective in small groups so that students can formulate questions and answer questions correctly and quickly. Through group collaboration, students in the MPI 2 Stambuk 2023 class help each other read English reading materials correctly, as stated by Anysah Dauly as a resource person who was willing to be interviewed, so that the next stage of English reading comprehension activities in the MPI 2 class can be carried out smoothly.

appropriate, such as summarizing reading, retelling, asking appreciative or applicable questions. Therefore, all students in the MPI 2 class will be more active in understanding English reading, so that they can speak English fluently.

DISCUSSION

During the discussion, the research results were explained at UINSU Campus II, MPI 2 semester 2 study program, located on Jl Wiliam Iskandar Pasar IV Percut Sei Tuan, Medan City, North Sumatra, Medan. Evaluation of the research results was given by sources who were willing to be interviewed, namely the MPI 2 Semester 2 study program. Therefore, it is important for this section to review the findings in the context of the existing literature and knowledge about the research subject. It is important to demonstrate our understanding of policy and practice. A discussion section needs to follow the results and link back to the literature review we used. Make sure everything we discuss is included in the results section. In picture 1. Conduct an interview with one of the MPI 2 classes, sister Ansyah Daulay, who is willing to provide information related to understanding English and students of the MPI 2 semester 2 study program.

From his statement, he said that MPI 2 semester 2 English reading comprehension was quite good, although there were still many mistakes and not everyone had mastered it, starting from how to read word by word, by sentence and up to paragraphs, he also said that MPI 2 semester 2 I have started to understand the meaning of every word in sentences and paragraphs. Although at the beginning he said that they also experienced very difficult problems in reading and interpreting each word, sentence and paragraph because it was difficult to read and difficult to interpret when each letter added, the meaning of the word being translated would be different. For other students in the MPI 2 semester 2 class who have not mastered reading comprehension and understanding to translate English, they are said to be or are classified as intermediate reading comprehension. Because for reading words or sentences, students who have not mastered it can read it, but for reading in one paragraph, students experience difficulty when speaking and when understanding the meaning of a paragraph of English text. If presented, those who understand English reading and also understand the meaning can get a percentage of 40% from 100%, which means the other 60% are still in the intermediate stage in understanding reading and meaning of English text. Students who understand how to read English have also experienced serious difficulties in reading when the letters and pronunciations are different, the way for students to quickly understand how to read English is by continuing and increasing their reading of English texts even though at the beginning they experience difficulties and difficulties. to pronounce it, increase the list of words and when you have memorized the list of words then implement them when we speak so that we don't forget easily and so that we get used to saying them. He also said that the MPI 2 course is also called an English course. They also gain knowledge from the course. However, only the material for practice is rarely done in class, so it is up to each student to practice it outside of the course with their friends first.

Documentation of Interviewing One of the MPI 2 Students

Discussions about English reading comprehension and MPI 2 students can involve several aspects, such as understanding English texts, reading strategies, and their influence on students. The following are several points that can be discussed in the discussion section of the journal. Discussion of English reading is an important skill for students mpi 2, especially in the context of academic studies. Students often face challenges in understanding English reading, especially when they have to

read scientific papers. Effective English reading comprehension can help students understand learning material and improve their learning outcomes. Several strategies that can be used including: reading quickly, using skimming and scanning techniques, taking notes, and identifying keywords. Using appropriate reading strategies can help students understand reading more easily. The influence of English reading comprehension on MPI 2 students is:

1. Good English reading comprehension can have a positive impact on student learning outcomes .
2. Students who are able to understand English reading well will find it easier to master learning material and produce quality scientific writing.
3. Comprehension of English reading can also help students develop critical and analytical thinking skills.

In discussions regarding English reading comprehension and MPI 2 students, it is also important to explain the importance of English reading comprehension, good reading strategies that can be used, and their impact on students. This discussion can provide better insight and understanding of the topic.

CONCLUSION

The English reading comprehension of UINSU MPI 2 semester 2 students is already quite good in English reading comprehension, students are even able to understand the meaning of English just by listening. It doesn't stop there, students also understand the meaning of each word, sentence, down to the paragraph. This understanding is obtained by students from English lessons in class for 2 credits on Wednesdays in the second hour. To improve understanding, students also carry out training to improve students' reading comprehension. On average, students use the training by reading continuously. with regularity, then students also increase their vocabulary by memorizing them and applying them in everyday life when speaking so they don't forget easily.

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